

New codes and data sets for the new moving point source model in EPISODE-CityChem v1.3

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1. The source codes and data sets for the new moving point source (MPS) model used in EPISODE-CityChem v1.3 are provided in this link.
 - source codes: The source codes for MPS model and modified line source (LS) codes for shipping emission modelling
 - simplified_1ship.zip: Input and output data sets for simplified study of shipping emission dispersion modelling with only 1 ship.
 - simplified_44ship.zip: Input and output data sets for simplified study of shipping emission dispersion modelling with 44 ships.
 - real_study.zip: Input and output data sets for real case study of shipping emission dispersion modelling

2. For new codes in “code_MPS”, they need to be copied to relevant sub-directories in EPISODE-CityChem v1.3 installation directory. It should be noted that the current version of MPS model can be used only for 1-hour simulation. Hence, the simulation needs to be updated every hour if a continuous simulation is conducted.
 - 2.1 New main codes needed to be copied:
 - New codes need to be copied to “src/point”: mod_psrc.f90, roldp.f90,rpsrc.f90, tspsrc.f90
 - New codes added to codes In “src/grid”: ricon.f90
 - 2.2 New codes in weather pre-processor (UECT):
 - New codes need to be copied to “preproc/uct/src”: emission_points.for; get_user_input.for; module_uct_exe.for; module_uct_io.for; output_citychem_pse.for.

3. For new codes in “code_line”, they need to be copied to relevant sub-directories in EPISODE-CityChem v1.3 installation directory. It should be noted that the codes modified here are used to shipping emission dispersion. If someone wants to use it for simulating cars or other emission sources, they may not update these codes to EPISODE and only use the original versions.
 - 3.1 New main codes needed to be copied:
 - New codes need to be copied to “src/point”: lsgrid.f90
 - 3.2 New codes in weather pre-processor (UECT):
 - New codes need to be copied to “preproc/uct/src”: emission_line.for; output_citychem_lse.for.